

IMPACT OF DIFFUSION OF INNOVATION ON CASHLESS TRANSACTION ADOPTION AND CONTINUED USAGE IN TARABA STATE

Galadima Talatu Obed

Office Technology and Management (OTM) Department
Federal Polytechnic, Bali, Taraba State Nigeria
talatuobed@gmail.com

Abstract

Financial systems are becoming more connected as the technology continues to advance. Cashless method transactions have been embraced by most economies around the world. This paper examined the impact of Diffusion of Innovation on the adoption of cashless transaction in Taraba State. Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) was integrated with some variables from Diffusion of Innovation (DOI) to form a theoretical framework. Structured questionnaire was used in collection of data. Research questions and hypotheses were formulated to help in carrying out the research work and Smart PLS was used in data analysis. The result revealed that Media influence and Social influence plays a very important role in shaping users behaviour in adopting cashless transactions.

Key Words: Cashless transactions, TAM, DOI, Payment system

Introduction

The world is continuously becoming a global village every day and financial systems continue to become more connected, most economies around the world have shifted to and the use of cashless method of payment to enhance quick, effective and safer delivery of financial task. This is more highly pronounced in the countries of the West and Asia where the technology of the usage of computers is cheaper and affordable. Many countries that adopted this system of payment have recorded a remarkable breakthrough and have boosted trade and other economic activities.

Nigeria and several other African countries before now transact with the heavy cash which has altered the growth in their economy and retard trade activities have now fall in line with the global trend (Okey, 2012).

The advancement in the Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in Nigerian has given birth to the need for adoption of this cashless policy in order to measure up with the global standards of trade and economy (Galadima, et al 2014).

The effort to reposition the nation's economy and make it relevant in the new global financial environment, make Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) continuously reformed the financial sector by encouraging E-payments and E-commerce. Much as the CBN tried to evolve a seamless system capable of installing a regime of stability in the monetary policy, the global world is continuously advancing to a more efficient and reliable ways to tackle challenges, this has necessitated the need for further reforms to meet up with this global challenges and advancement in technology as imposed on technocrats by the devastating contradictions in the socio-economic environment (Nwankwo and Eze, 2012).

In the recent times the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN), has engaged in series of reforms aimed both at making the Nigerian financial system formidable and enhancing the overall performance of the country so it can be placed on the path that tune to global trend (Akhahlume and Ohiokha, 2012).

This research will focus on how this cashless policy will be of benefit to the citizens and inhabitants of Taraba State, The state is blessed with many natural resources that attract the attention of many marketers for business and other activities, hence it is important that this cashless policy be adopted for quick and safe transactions.

Statement of Problem

Over the years in the course of history, there have been different modes of transactions which changes as technology advances to the present day modern ways of transactions. The primitive ways of transactions which include trade by barter had a number of problems with the prominent one being the double coincidence of wants which necessitated the introduction of various forms of money. This eventually led to the emergence of potentially superior substitute for cash or monetary exchanges, that is the manual banking system, the electronic

banking system. Finally, the recent advocate for a cashless economy and mobile money implementation by the Central Bank of Nigeria in line with the global payments evolution is another substitute for cash. This is to drive development and modernization of our payment system to corroborate the Nigeria's vision 2020 goal of being amongst the top 20 economies by the year 2020.

The introduction of cashless economy had gained a number of reactions over the adoption of e-payment and cashless economy (or cashless banking), which implies in concrete terms, that people have not been convinced that the agenda is for the good of all. It implies that not enough has been done to address the genuine concerns of the citizenry about the cashless transactions. This paper aimed at studying the impact of Diffusion of Innovation on the adoption of cashless transactions in Taraba State.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study is to investigate the adoption and prospects of cashless transactions among Taraba State citizenry which are specifically listed below:

- (i) To investigate the degree of awareness of cashless transactions among Taraba citizenry and its adoption
- (ii) To ascertain the prospects of cashless transactions in Taraba State.

Research Question

- (i) What is the degree of awareness of cashless transactions among Taraba citizenry and its adoption?
- (ii) What are the prospects of cashless transactions in Taraba State?

Population of the Study

The population of this study was taken from customers of all the available banks in Taraba State

Sample Selection

The probability sampling technique was used since the result will be used to generalize where sample will be taken randomly from customers with e-banking

experience and/or one-time users of e-banking. Number of customers was sampled from seven local governments of Taraba State. These local governments comprises of two from each of the three regions of the state and also the state capital (Bali - 100, Gashaka - 100, Jalingo - 100, Karim-Lamido - 100, Zing – 100, Takum - 100, Wukari - 100) which will form the total of 700 customers in all sixteen local governments

Instrument for Data Collection

In this paper work, Questionnaire was developed after reviewing several literatures, which gathered information about the respondent's perception about cashless economy in Taraba State. The seven point scale was adopted for the statements of the questionnaire ranging from 1 – 7, 1 for strongly disagreed, 2 for disagreed, 3 for slightly disagreed, 4 for neutral, 5 for slightly agreed, 6 for agreed and 7 for strongly agreed.

Method of Data Collection

Data was collected by the researcher from the banks in the seven Local Governments from the three regions of Taraba State. These Local Governments are those with or without operational banks but whose citizen patronizes banks within or outside the Local Government Area

Overview of Cashless Economy in Nigeria

A cashless economy according to Adu (2016), is an environment in which money is spent without being physically carried from one place to another. Innovations in information technologies according to (Costa and Paul, 2001) have improved the prospects for the advent of a cashless society. Although it remains unclear whether the new information technologies will drive out cash completely from the payments system in the foreseeable future, the prospects for such an outcome cannot be excluded either.

Akhahlumeh and Ohiokha, Yaqub and colleagues (Akhahlumeh and Ohiokha, 2012 & Yaqub et al, 2013) highlight that, cashless economy contrary to what is suggestive of the term by some Nigerians, does not refer to an outright absence of cash transactions in the economic setting but to the one in which the amount of cash-based transactions are reduced to the barest minimum. It is simply an

economic setting where goods and services are bought and paid for through electronic media (Nweke, 2012).

According to Akhahlumeh and Ohiokha, (Akhahlumeh and Ohiokha, 2012), in a cashless economy, the money in your wallet or purse is practically irrelevant. You can pay for your purchase by any one of the abundant of credit cards or bank transfer. Some aspects of the functioning of the cashless economy Ernest, 2012 added, are enhanced by e-banking, e-payment, e-commerce; mobile banking, among others, which all refers to how transactions and payments are effected in a cashless economy.

The Central Bank of Nigeria, CBN, has reeled out final operational guidelines (which can be obtained from the CBN website) for the implementation of the cashless policy. Indeed, Nigeria remains a largely cash-based economy with cash payments contributing over 80% of retail and commercial transactions with its implication for cost of cash management to the banking industry, security, money laundering, among others (Ochei, 2012).

Less developed countries or in a more euphemistic description “developing countries”, are plagued with the feature of the existence of a dual economy; this is an economic situation where there is an existence of the formal sector with its technological advances and the informal sector with its crude solutions to modern day problems. However, these different sections of the economy are serviced by the very same financial system which has undergone reforms in line with the realities of the global financial system, as noted in Nigeria, the case being studied here. Therefore, there is the need to discover the implications of introducing e-money, in an economic system that is a composite of the informal and formal sectors.

While it is evident that the cashless policy might be advantageous to the economy, many argue that the relevant conditions necessary for its effective take-off were not yet in place. According to this school of thought, the CBN attempt was akin to placing the cart before the horse. Invariably, this raises the fundamental question of what conditions are necessary for the smooth take-off

and sustenance of the policy, for Nigeria to optimally maximize the benefits. Are the banks and people equipped to embrace such policy considering our present level of development? Simply put, is Nigeria ripe for a cashless economy, given the inundation of multiple negatives that confront her? (Ernest and Fadiya, 2012)

The implementation of the CBN cash-less policy however, commenced in Lagos (Cash-less Lagos) with effect from the 1st of January, 2012. As part of the policy cash in transit (CIT) to merchant-customers are to be rendered by the CBN licenced CIT providers at a fee rather than the Digital Multimedia Broadcasting (DMBs) with effect from the 1st of January, 2012.

The full implementation of the cash-less policy commenced on the 1st of April, 2012 in Lagos with the following amendments to the guidelines:

- i. A daily cumulative limit of N500, 000.00 and N3, 000,000.00 on free cash withdrawals and lodgments by individual and corporate customers, respectively.
- ii. Individuals and corporate organizations that make cash cumulative withdrawals above the limits would be charged a processing fee of 3 per cent and 5 per cent respectively.
- iii. Cash deposits above the limits will attract a processing fee of 2 percent and 3 per cent for individuals and corporate organizations, respectively.
- iv. Exemptions are granted to Ministries, Departments and Agencies (MDAs) of the Federal and State governments for the purpose of revenue collection as well as direct lodgements and withdrawals of Primary Mortgage Banks (PMBs) and Microfinance Banks (MFBs) in recognition of the nature of their operations.
- v. Third party cheques above N150, 000.00 shall not be eligible for encashment over the counter. Value for such cheques shall be received through the clearing house (Akhalmeh and Ohiokha, 2012).

Furthermore, the Bank continued with the implementation of the following initiatives, to ensure the success of cash-less Lagos:

- Engagement of relevant stakeholders by the Nigeria Electronic Fraud Forum (NEFF) to ensure that a collaborative industry board is put in place to proactively manage e-fraud attempts and limit losses.
- Transformation of Nigeria Interbank Settlement System (NIBSS) plc to effectively play the role of Payments Terminal Service Aggregator (PTSA) (Nweke, 2012).

Benefits of Cashless Economy

The cashless policy, if successfully implemented according to Okey (2012), has potential benefits such as: reduction in cost associated with cash-based economy, reduction in the risk of using physical cash (armed robbery or burglary and disaster like fire outbreaks), reducing the subsidy of cash transaction cost incurred in cash-based economy, arresting the problem of informal economy by reducing the amount of cash outside the banks or formal economy, reducing cases of corruption and money laundering encouraged by cash-based economy, faster transaction and improving hygiene by eliminating bacteria through handling of notes, among others.

Okey (2012) summarized the benefits expected to be derived by various stakeholders from an increased utilization of the e-payment systems in the country as follows:

For Consumers: Increased convenience; more service options; reduced risk of cash-related crimes; cheaper access to banking services and access to credit.

For Corporations: Faster access to capital; reduced revenue leakage; and reduced cash handling costs.

For Government: Increased tax collections; greater financial inclusion; increased economic development.

Other countries especially those from western part of the world already embrace and are operating the cashless economy. Looking at the economies of those

countries, we must readily accept the fact that these are economies with functional institutions, which cannot be said about Nigeria with conviction (Akhahlumeh and Ohiokha, 2012).

Frame of Reference

Technology Acceptance Model

The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) is an information systems theory that models how users come to accept and use a technology that will encourage economic growth (Davis, 2003). The model suggests that when users are presented with a new technology, a number of factors influence their decision about how and when they will use it, notably: Perceived usefulness (PU) defined as "the degree to which a person believes that using a particular system would enhance his or her job performance. And Perceived ease-of-use (PEOU) - also defined as "the degree to which a person believes that using a particular system would be free from effort.

The TAM is being widely used and proven model of investigating user's adoption of information systems. People tend to use an application to the extent they believe it will aid their performance (Lee, et.al, 2003 & Adesina et.al, 2010).

Fig1. Technology Acceptance Source: Davis,

Research model and Hypothesis

In this work, TAM is being extended with DOI. This is achieved by introducing some other constructs and subsequently measures their effect on the adoption and

acceptance of cashless economy in Taraba State. The extended TAM includes the external variables “Difusion of Innovation”. To achieve this task, a conceptual model was developed as shown in Figure 2 as a search light for hypotheses formulation and its analysis. The arrows linking constructs (latent variables) specify hypothesized relationships in the direction of arrows. The arrows between constructs and indicators (observed variables) indicate measurement validity. Perceived ease of use, perceived usefulness and DOI can be considered cognitive constructs.

Fig. 2 Proposed conceptual model

Research hypotheses

H1a: Perceived ease of use positively influences attitudes towards adopting or continuing to use cashless transactions.

H1b: Perceived ease of use positively influences adoption or continue to use cashless transactions.

H1c: Perceived ease of use positively influences Perceived Usefulness towards adopting or continue to use cashless transactions.

H2: Attitude positively influences the intention to adopt or continue to use cashless transactions.

H3: Perceived usefulness positively influences attitudes towards adopting or continuing to use cashless transactions.

H4: Media influence has a positive effect on social influence.

H5: Social influence has a positive effect on a person's attitude towards cashless transactions

Results and Discussion

Analysis of Model and Hypothesis Testing

The reliability of the model was measured with the use of composite reliability (α) for all the constructs that was used (see table 1). There is an indication that the result obtained is consistent with recommended cut-off level of 0.70 [46], since the constructs ranged between 0.70690 and 0.898901.

Table1. Composite Reliability

Construct	Composite reliability
Attitude	0.884183
Adoption	0.893413
Media Influence	0.884479
Perceived Usefulness	0.856284
Social Influence	0.779839

I further evaluated the hypothesised constructs with the use of T-statistics so as to obtain the relationship between the constructs and their observed indicators as outlined in Table 2.

Result and Hypotheses Testing

The result of testing structural links of the research model using PLS analysis is represented in Table 2. The estimated path coefficients are given along with associated t-values.

Table 2: Coefficients of determination

Hypotheses	Effect	Path Coefficient	T - Statistics	Remark
H1a	PEOU -> AT	0.107**	2.888590	Supported
H1b	PEOU -> AD	0.260***	5.371639	Supported
H1c	PEOU -> PU	0.446***	11.240063	Supported
H2	AT -> AD	0.360***	7.331517	Supported
H3	PU -> AT	0.192***	3.991886	Supported
H4	MI -> SI	0.386***	9.286582	Supported
H5	SI -> AT	0.352***	7.419336	Supported

Figure 3 describes graphically the relationships between constructs and observed indicators of the hypotheses testing showing the various paths and their levels of significances.

The overall result shows that adopting and operating cashless economy is predicted by Perceived ease of use ($\beta=260$, $p<0.001$), Attitude ($\beta=0.360$, $p<0.001$),. Attitude is predicted by perceived ease of use ($\beta=0.107$, $p<0.01$), perceived usefulness ($\beta=0.192$, $p<0.001$), and Social influence ($\beta=0.352$, $p<0.001$). Perceived usefulness is predicted by perceived ease of use ($\beta=0.446$, $p<0.001$). Social influence is predicted by Media influence ($\beta=0.386$, $p<0.001$).

Conclusion

This study shows that recognizing both technological and awareness issues play an important role in users' behaviour to adopt and continue to cashless transaction. The TAM constructs as discussed in this work are regarded as the fundamental criterion required to determine the behavioural intention to adopt cashless transaction. Other conciliators (such as attitude) equally contributed their own influence adoption of cashless transaction. This implies that to effectively attract users to adopt and continues to use cashless transactions; attention needs to be paid to those aspects. Awareness also contributed some levels of significant influence on users' attitude towards adopting and continued usage of cashless transactions. Since all the Diffusion of Innovation constructs– Media influence and Social influence emerged as positive factors in the adoption of cashless transaction, then DOI (Diffusion of Innovation) helps in broadening the user's knowledge on the importance of cashless transactions. The result of this research work presents a confirmation of the appropriateness of the integration of TAM with DOI for explaining individual behaviour thereby provides support for the links added to represent the impact of DOI on attitude and behavioural intention in the adoption and continued usage of cashless transactions.

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